

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Nwangwu**FIRST NAME:** Chiugo**PROGRAM CODE:** DSDD**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** RP1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 6 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Basics of writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-9)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 7)
3. American versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 28-32)
4. Rules of thumb (EUCLID 2019, 14)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2019, 24)
6. Correction to papers (EUCLID 2019, 36-40)

ESSENTIAL CONCEPTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) THE SUMMARY

The decision to enroll for my doctorate was really to deepen my knowledge and expertise in my chosen profession. With this background, I approached the joining email and course material with zeal. The main goal of ACA-401D is to get us familiar with EUCLID guidelines, templates, and technology for the duration of the programme. I found the documents easy to read with novel knowledge. It allowed me view English language with fresh eyes. I learned how to; use the templates, save documents, use Zotero for citing, write with focus, and adhere to guidelines. The concept of “balancing my essay” by thinking creatively and critically was a major learning.

Particularly adding samples of previous response papers, correction sample of assignments and step by step on writing assignments was instructional for me. What also worked well for me was in being deliberate in forgetting any previous knowledge on this subject. A full immersion of myself helped me get through the first period. My goal is to apply the same elements of learning all through the duration of this course.

2) MY REACTION TO THE STUDY MATERIAL

The reading material defines academic essay writing as one that “aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EULID 2019, 1). The essay development process is rigorous which involved reading and highlighting the different reading materials provided. The essay should also answer the question posed; in this case I coined my question or theme as the essential concepts of academic writing. I focused on gaining a fresh understanding of what essay writing is from the EUCLID perspective so that I could learn better. In the past, I reasoned essay writing as the usual communication of an idea without any need to have evidence and construct a plan. My work life over the years has seen me respond to issues by writing, without following a plan, presenting with flow and showing evidence to back up claims. It was really focused on getting the response out there and communicating clearly. After the studying the materials for period one, I see the gaps in my writing. Also evidence based writing provides objectivity, reduces bias and prevents potential issues that might arise from copying, false claims or misrepresentation of facts.

The concept of balancing my essay stood out for me. EUCLID (2019) coursepack mentions the necessity to find balance when combining creative and critical thinking when writing (EUCLID 2019, 2). This suggests some preparatory work in academic essay development the need to; manage time effectively, earmark enough time to develop a well thought piece and identify potential source documents that will serve as evidence to support my ideas. For this period, the reading materials seemed a lot to start with, however this quickly changed. I allowed days to read the documents provided and get familiar with navigating the different sources. The coursepack recommends to; start reading early, taking notes, highlighting concepts and pages, and asking reflective questions (ibid.).

The checklist on how to write a response paper is a valuable resource for self-checking my progress in writing the period one (1) response paper. It provided clarity and focus in getting the response paper ready. Period one (1) is a reminder that I have started a new journey in life. Paramount for me is in how the new material and concepts can be applied to my realities especially at work. A concept I have already started applying is in the use of grammarly to edit my document. I observe, however, I am not able to reference some of the reading material, to be specific; the student orientation document. This was the first document I read to familiarize myself with the EUCLID guidelines. I would assume this as a general knowledge because grammarly is an open source data and thus there is no need to cite (EUCLID 2019, 9). The study material deepened my understanding of the different concepts in academic essay writing which I want to highlight.

a) Plagiarism

As scholars, I have a good knowledge of what plagiarism is. A new learning from reading the coursepack is in how to cite a long quote of more than 4 lines. They are

treated differently and placed in a new paragraph, indented and will take no quotation marks (EUCLID 2019, 7). The material is instructive and provides clear guidelines I will follow to reduce the risk of writing a plagiarized document. More important, the teachings on citation, proper referencing, and paraphrasing are aimed at maintaining integrity in academic writing (Adler-Kassner, Anson, and Howard 2008, 7). I have always used the Harvard style referencing which in comparison to the Turabian is less simple. Access to the EUCLID templates, referencing software and detail in every document has made me enthusiastic to follow through obtaining a doctorate.

b) American versus British English

More similarities than differences are seen in the standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE). Culture and national histories are the main variants between the two and is explored across several categories. The challenge in adhering to the SAE during this academic journey is that of using the right spelling consistently. It was interesting to learn about euphemistic references, though the coursepack should have done more to show how each nationality uses euphemism. The categories should have been explained better. In my quest to find out why SAE is more the recommended style, I found that it provides the professional balance required to communicate effectively in any setting including; school, work and with peers. Students are encouraged to understand and use the SAE to prepare them better for professional communication

c) Rules of thumb and style guide

The concepts of writing quality papers will require getting used to. From preparing this concept paper I have just learned about the use of signal phrases, when not to cite and acceptable paraphrasing (EUCLID 2019, 10). Still, I am concerned about being more focused on following all the rules to the detriment of deep thinking.

The means of documenting an approach to writing defines a style guide (EUCLID 2019, 24). The coursepack teaches about different writing styles; technical, commercial or business, journalism, and web copywriting. I understand now the concept of maintaining consistency in writing. The coursepack clearly provides detailed aspects of what the response paper and master paper should be. The example of a good response paper provided as one of the reading materials is a quality resource document for me. I consistently referred to it for guidance all through writing my response for period one (EUCLID 2020, 5).

d) Correction to papers

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3) CONCLUSION

Writing my response paper for period 1 is the first step towards quality academic submissions. Reading the study materials, notice that the EUCLID culture is focused, clear and consistent. I was concerned about the materials initially because I did not know what to expect but the “how to write a response paper” eased me into writing. The first concept on essay writing clearly defined the basics, how to plan my writing, and nudged me to view academic writing differently. When I was studying for a master’s degree, focus was largely on referencing and plagiarism, in comparison now to an in-depth focus on academic writing, Zotero for referencing, writing styles, how to use grammarly and proper language use. A concern for me is how to make certain my sentences are not long. I did not consider this as one of the issues in my academic submissions.

This period has expanded my knowledge in; essay development, writing style guide, citation, plagiarism and standard use of templates. Eagerly, I downloaded the necessary software and have started using these in my assignments. EUCLID has provided a roadmap for me to improve my writing, expand my knowledge and importantly set clear expectations from a doctorate candidate.

REFERENCES

- Adler-Kassner, Linda, Chris M. Anson, and Rebecca Moore Howard. 2008. “Framing Plagiarism.” In *Originality, Imitation, and Plagiarism*, edited by Caroline Eisner and Martha Vicinus. Teaching Writing in the Digital Age. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv65sxxk1.23> (accessed on July 18, 2020).
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